

MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES BY SEGMENTATION AND ASSEMBLY

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1. General Introduction

Segmentation and assembly has been recognized as an attractive approach to create hybrid materials [1] with novel, and multifunctional properties. This material design principle can be applied to multiple length scales ([2]-[4]), Fig. 1.

Segmentation and assembly is a mechanism that has been found in several biological structures (e.g. spinal column, armadillo armor, shark tesserae) where toughness is combined with flexibility. Such structures are assembled in a close packed configuration by connecting individual hard through a common carrier. The present paper discusses two examples of such an approach in the context of multi-phase material systems. In the first example, a composite material is demonstrated in which a segmented matrix of topologically interlocked unit elements is combined with carbon fibers. This composite possesses characteristics of a tensegrity structure. In the second example a multi-layer composite is discussed in which a segmented “tile” layer is assembled on a compliant substrate, inspired by tesserae. This material exhibits dynamic response with rich sub and superharmonics.

2. Tensegrity Composite

Tensegrity structures combine continuous tension and discontinuous compression elements [5]. This study investigates the design of such a bio-inspired engineering material that could replicate the function and characteristics of the aforementioned natural structures, and, interrogates the resulting material in regards to its mechanical properties. However, manmade tensegrity structures, made of cables and struts, are not dense. An approach is presented to use the principles of segmentation and assembly to create tensegrity systems in a space filling form. The approach employs the concept of topological interlocking materials (TIMs) [6]. In TIMs,

independent unit elements in the shape of polyhedral are arranged such that each element is prevented from moving by surrounding elements. Our work in particular considers such assemblies created in the form of the densest 2D packing of tetrahedra. Under transverse loading polyhedral elements transfer load to each other through contact only. To fulfill equilibrium, a tensile load carrying component is needed. In past studies by our group ([7], [8]) as well as by others ([9]-[12]), the assembly of polyhedra was located within rigid abutments. Here, a different and alternative approach is undertaken, and tensile loads are carried by strings positioned between the polyhedra. In the embodiment of specific concern to the present investigation, the tensegrity TIMs were created using 49 tetrahedra unit elements (made of ABS and produced in a 3D printer) of edge length 25mm. Carbon fiber tow (T300) was used as the tension carrying component with the fiber tow weaved into the tetrahedra assembly. Fig. 2 depicts the manufacturing approach. First, the topologically interlocked assembly of tetrahedra is obtained. At this stage, the polyhedra are positioned on an underlying template (a periodic arrangement of square pyramids), Fig. 2(a).

Subsequently, the carbon fiber tow is placed between the tetrahedra such that a weave pattern is created with the tetrahedra positioned in void space in the weave, Fig. 2(b). Finally, the carbon fiber tow is tightened by a knot using a lock-nut assembly. Other processes for locking can be employed based on well known rules to tie knots. This process is controlled by inserting a thin film pressure sensor between tetrahedral such that the interelement contact pressure is controlled. The final assembly is depicted in Fig. 2(c). The two pairs (white and yellow) boundary elements were introduced for convenience of the assembly and weaving process,

but dense tensegrity assemblies can be created without these.

The resulting two-dimensional solid was subjected to transverse loading. Typical force-deflection data from such experiments are depicted in Fig. 3. The recorded force-deflection data show a non-linear hardening response. Such a response is has been documented for classical, sparse tensegrity structures [13] and is related to the geometry of the load transfer in the assembly and the changes of geometry of the load transfer in the structure during loading. We observe the load carrying capacity of the assembly to be limited by two possible failure modes: (i) partial rupture of the carbon fibers, and (ii) by in-plane rotation of the central tetrahedron. Fig. 4 depicts a typical tensegrity structure after failure.

To demonstrate further embodiments of the dense tensegrity, Fig. 5(a) provides an image of a material system where no surrounding boundary elements are employed. The mechanical response is in principle identical to that depicted in Fig. 3, but the peak load – recovery response is more strongly present, Fig. 5(b). This figure also compares the response of the tensegrity system with that of an assembly as supported by rigid abutments.

The analysis approach for the dense tensegrity systems introduced here expands on the concepts of thrust line analysis for topologically interlocked materials as introduced by the present authors in [7] This approach recognizes that load transfer in topologically interlocked assemblies occurs by contact between elements only. For the purpose of the development of an analysis of transverse load transfer the topologically interlocked assembly is replaced by a network of trusses located in the thrust lines. A mechanics of materials approach is used to solve the statically indeterminate system resulting from this approach. Here, relevant modifications for the approach to the topologically interlocked dense tensegrity are made.

The location of the thrust lines in the tensegrity system is obtained from a finite element model, Fig. 6.

An abstraction of the configuration of Fig. 7 is used to obtain a closed form expression for the force-deflection response. This model follows from [14]. The mechanical response of the tensegrity system emerge as a result of a self equilibrated internal stress state. We consider the tensegrity system as an assembly of trusses and strings in a geometry as given in Fig. 7.

The following relationships emerge:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F &= 2F_s \sin \beta; \beta \approx \frac{\delta}{L_0} \\
 \frac{F_s L_0}{E_s A_s} &= L - L_0 = \frac{\tilde{\delta}}{\sin \beta} - L_0; \\
 \sin \beta &\approx \beta - \frac{\beta^3}{3!} = \beta - \frac{\beta^3}{6} = \frac{\delta}{L_0} \left(1 - \frac{\delta^2}{6L_0^2} \right); \\
 \Rightarrow \frac{F_s L_0}{E_s A_s} &= \frac{\delta^2}{6L_0} \Rightarrow F = E_s A_s \frac{\delta^3}{3L_0^3} \Rightarrow F = C \delta^3
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here, F_s is the force in the string, and, F is the transverse load, respectively. Furthermore, δ is the transverse deflection and β the characteristic internal angle. The system characteristic constant C is determined by the string stiffness and the geometry of the assembly. For the comparison between experimental data (considering the experiment in which string failure was observed, Fig. 3) and model prediction we employ this description in a normalized form which allows for the determination of the system characteristic constant and its change during loading:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{F}{F_{\max}} &= \tilde{C} \delta^3 \\
 \tilde{C} &= 1.0 \text{mm}^{-3} \text{ for } \delta \in (0.0\text{mm}, 14.1\text{mm}) \\
 \tilde{C} &= 0.04 \text{mm}^{-3} \text{ for } \delta \in (14.2\text{mm}, 26.2\text{mm}) \\
 \tilde{C} &= 0.001 \text{mm}^{-3} \text{ for } \delta \in (26.3\text{mm}, 30.0\text{mm})
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The comparison between experiment and model is depicted in Fig. 8.

Based on the model we can now argue the proposed dense tensegrity system can allow for variable system stiffness by controlled changes to the string stiffness. Fig. 9 depicts model predictions of the force deflection response where the string stiffness was set to decline throughout the loading processes.

3. Tesseract Composite

Tesseract composites are assemblies of stiff tiles on flexible substrates. These systems are inspired by the anatomical structure of tesseract in sharks and rays [15], and allow for high mechanical efficiency. A model tesseract material system was created by 3D printing an assembly of 9 rigid square tiles onto a compliant substrate. The manufacture of the tesseract composite was conducted in a Connex 350 3D printer, and the use of the flexible TangoBlack+ and rigid VeroWhite materials. The Connex printer enables the integrated 3D printing of such multi-material assemblies. Trenches of width of 250 μm between tiles were considered such that individual tiles are not completely integrated after the initial print process but only weakly connected. The actual tile separation can then be accomplished by fracturing along these predefined lines. The resulting tesseract composite is depicted in Fig. 10.

The tesseract composite possesses a bi-linear bending stiffness, with a stiff response when the tile-to-tile contact is closed, and compliant response when the tile-to-tile contacts are open. In order to demonstrate the interesting characteristics of such a bilinear tesseract composite structure the transmission characteristics of sound across the structure are explored.

First a finite element model of a simplified tesseract composite was created. This model structure consisted of a compliant backing ($E=2$ GPa) and a stiff tile material ($E=200$ GPa) in a planar configuration with span 0.5 m, which considered a minimal assembly of two tiles across the span, Fig. 11. The contact interaction between the tiles assumed a contact stiffness of $10E14$ Pa/m. The model possesses a bilinear stiffness in its deflection response under a constant distributed load with the bending stiffness in the open direction 1.0 Pa/m and that in the closed direction 1.4 Pa/m.

In order to assess the acoustical characteristics of the tesseract composite a 2D model of a standing wave tube was created, with the tesseract composite separating upstream from downstream duct. An implicit dynamic simulation was conducted with the code ABAQUS. Fig. 12 depicts the geometry of the set-up considered.

This approach allows one to include the non-linear response due to the contact interaction. The acoustic analysis considered pure tone sound sources both above and below the fundamental frequency. The time history of the pressure response was recorded at several locations of the acoustic duct. Then the power spectral density (PSD) of the response signal was obtained using Welch's average modified periodogram method. In addition to the transient analysis, steady state analysis of limiting structures were conducted as well which considered the open and closed states separately. For the open configuration the first eigenmode possesses a frequency of 45.4 Hz, while for the closed configuration the first eigenmode possesses a frequency of 48.4 Hz. The first eigenfrequency of the bilinear system was then computed as

$$f_{Bi} = \frac{2f_{open}f_{closed}}{f_{open} + f_{closed}} \quad (3)$$

with a numerical value of $f_{Bi}=46.2$ Hz.

The numerical simulation of the single frequency transient response were considered at a frequency below f_{Bi} ($f=20$ Hz), at f_{Bi} , and above f_{Bi} ($f=80$ Hz). Results for these three cases are depicted in the subsequent figures and for each frequency compared to a system with linear stiffness. In addition for the frequency f_{Bi} the directionality of the system was investigated.

The results in Fig. 14 to 16 indicate the presence of subharmonics and superharmonics. Both are excited in the tesseract composites in addition to the excitation frequency. In the linear comparison material subharmonics and superharmonics are absent. The details of the response are found to be dependent on the relative location of the excitation frequency to the structure eigenmodes. The above

results support the idea of transferring energy from low frequencies to higher frequencies, and that tesserae composites can play a role in advanced acoustical materials. The material system provides the freedom to tune the strength of the superharmonics and subharmonics by increasing or decreasing the degree of bilinearity through either the mismatch in modulus of tile and backing, the contact interaction as well as the degree of segmentation.

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Fig. 1: Segmentation and assembly as a principle of hybrid material design across length scales ([2]-[4]).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2: (a) Topologically interlocked tetrahedra of edge length a ; (b) Weaving pattern; (c) Final dense tensegrity assembly based on topologically interlocked assembly of tetrahedra.

Fig. 3: Mechanical response of the dense tensegrity assemblies under transverse loading. Comparison to a topologically interlocked material assembly supported by abutments.

Fig. 4: Structure after failure.

(a)

Fig. 5: (a) Dense tensegrity structure, no boundary elements; (b) mechanical response.

Fig. 6: Computed spatial distribution of compressive principal stresses in a transversely loaded dense tensegrity. The red line depicts the spring elements representing the strings of the weave.

Fig. 7: Model system to obtain the mechanical response of the tensegrity system. Black lines represent the thrust lines in the tetrahedra, while gray lines represent the carbon fiber tow.

Fig. 8: Comparison of model prediction and experiment.

Fig. 10: 3D printed model tesserae composite.

Fig. 9: Predicted mechanical response of a dense tensegrity system with controlled string stiffness during the loading sequence.

Fig. 11: A model of a minimal tesserae assembly.

Fig. 12: (a) Geometry of the acoustic system considered in the finite element simulation. (b) The test sample is considered as the minimal tesserae composite depicted in Fig. 10.

Fig. 14: Predicted power spectral density (PSD) for (a) the tesserae model and (b) an unsegmented system. $f_{Bi} = f = 46.2$ Hz.

Fig. 13: Predicted power spectral density (PSD) for (a) the tesserae model and (b) an unsegmented system. $f=20$ Hz.

Fig. 15: Predicted power spectral density (PSD) for (a) the tesserae model and (b) an unsegmented system. $f_{Bi} = f = 46.2$ Hz. Reverse loading direction.

Fig. 16: Predicted power spectral density (PSD) for (a) the tesserae model and (b) an unsegmented system. $f = 80$ Hz.